

ISic0080

Funerary inscription for an Abbot (?)

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ietas

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Iato

Provenance

Found in the area of mediaeval houses built over the south-east corner of the agora

Coordinates

37.966807, 13.198520

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Monte Iato, Antiquarium Case d'Alia e parco archeologico Monte Iato, inventory I.14

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of a marble slab broken on all sides, and re-used on the less smooth reverse side for a Latin inscription; the upper right corner may be preserved

Dimensions

Height 30.5 cm

Width cm

Depth 2.5 cm

Layout

Remains of parts of four lines of Latin text, probably the upper right section of the text, with vacat in the upper right

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Hicrequies]ciṭ
2. [inpacefam]ulus D(e)i
3. [---][a]bba[s]
4. [qui vixit an(nos)] p,(us) [m(inus)][---]

Apparatus

Text of Rizzone 2009, with minor modification line 4 (after photo)

Isler: CII;

Isler: [Pa]ulus(?); Isler, Bivona: D(omin)i

Isler: [---].I[---]; Rizzone [qui vixit an(nos)] pl(us) m(inus)[---]

Translation (en)

Here lies in peace the servant of God, Abbot [(name)], who lived [--] years, more or less

Translation (it)

Qui giace in pace il servo di Dio [---] abate, che visse piu o meno anni [--]

Commentary

Rizzone 2009 reconstructs this as a rare record (for Sicily) of a member of a monastic order, in the context of discussing a funerary inscription from Mineo (ISic3454 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3454>]) which appears to record a monk.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492395

EDCS 45600021

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1997-1998. Epigrafia Latina. *Kokalos*. 43-44: 613-624. At 613

Isler, H. P. 1994. Monte Iato: la ventiquattresima campagna di scavo. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 85-86: 27-47. At 30-31 fig.13

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni tardoantiche da Mineo (CT). *Epigraphica*. 71: 426-437. At 433 fig.4

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Photo from SicArch 85/86 p.31 fig.13